

Assessing the potential of water spinach leaves (*Ipomoea aquatica* Forsk., Family: Convolvulaceae) extract used as anti-inflammatory agent

Menard D. Cayton¹, Winifred S. Orgah¹, Rabia A. Sahipa¹, Carolyn T. Yu¹, Anthony R. Marin^{2*}

¹Pharmacy Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

²School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: amarin@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

*For a long time, plants and plant derivatives have been used as a source of medicine. Nature's gift to humans is medicinal plants, which enable them to live a disease-free and healthy life. They are essential in maintaining our health. In extreme necessity such as physical illness brought by a hostile environment, the primitive man was forced to make a frantic search for a remedy. Inflammation is a defense mechanism in the body. It is part of the body's immune response. The immune system recognizes damaged cells, irritants, and pathogens, and it begins the healing process. When something harmful or irritating affects a part of our body, there is a biological response to try to remove it. In the present study using different concentrations of *Ipomoea aquatica* from 100 mg/dose, 200 mg/dose, and 400 mg/dose along with different extracts such as ethanol extract, petroleum ether extract, chloroform extract used in the treatment for anti-inflammatory activity along with distilled water for negative control and naproxen for positive control in the carrageenan-induced rat paw edema. The investigation showed that the ethyl acetate extract with the concentration of 200 mg/dose and 400 mg/dose showed the closest effect compared to the standard (naproxen) while the other groups showed a mild inhibition of the inflammation in carrageenan-induced paw edema. Also, the significant of the ethyl acetate extract may be attributed to their high content of flavonoids.*

Keywords: Anti-inflammatory, extract, water spinach, *Ipomoea aquatica*, Convolvulaceae flavonoids, inflammation models.

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Introduction

For a long time, plants and plant derivatives have been used as a source of medicine (Michael et al., 2013). Nature's gift to humans is medicinal plants, which enable them to live a disease-free and healthy life. They used to prevent or cure disease and play a vital role in preserving our health. The Philippines is very rich in and fully endowed with natural resources including suitable land for medicinal plants and vegetables which can be used for various purposes. In extreme necessity such as physical illness brought by a hostile environment, the primitive man was forced to make a frantic search for a remedy (Katkar et al., 2010).

Some diseases that are associated with inflammation including distinct types of rheumatic diseases are one of the major problems. One of the defense mechanisms of the body is inflammation. It is part of the body's biological response. The damaged cells, irritants, and pathogens, and it begins the healing process are recognized by the immune system (Gomaa et al., 2018). When something irritating or harmful affects a part of our body, the body's immune response tries to remove it. Although inflammation can be uncomfortable, it is evident that the body is attempting to cure itself (Shah & Mehta, 2012). Redness, swelling, warmth, and sometimes discomfort and immobility are all signs of inflammation (Yang et al., 2013; Szalay, 2018).

Anti-inflammatory drugs are commonly used to treat inflammation. The most common anti-inflammatory drugs are over-the-counter medications such as aspirin, naproxen, and ibuprofen. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) can be taken to alleviate the pain caused by inflammation. They are frequently prescribed for short-term ailments such as headaches, fevers associated with colds and flu, menstrual cycles, and strained or injured muscles. They can also be used to treat chronic illnesses like arthritis and back pain, though this is usually done at the discretion of the doctor. Sometimes they are used for post-surgery pain treatment in prescription doses but can cause a lot of side effects. Therefore, herbal drugs can be a potential source to replace them. Every year, a large number of plants from the traditional medicinal system are screened for anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities, but only a few are approved for use in the health care system after clinical trials (Yuan et al., 2016).

Methodology

Research Design

The leaves extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* underwent scientific investigation for its anti-inflammatory properties. The researchers conducted a biological test in assessing the potential of *Ipomoea aquatica* extract as an anti-inflammatory agent. This study was conducted at Mots Animal House, Sta. Rosa, Laguna.

Research Procedure

Plant materials

The fresh leaves of *Ipomoea aquatica* were collected from Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines. The plant sample of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves was washed thoroughly with water and dried in the oven at 60°C for 24 hours.

Chemicals and Reagents

These reagents are used for the extraction and treatment of anti-inflammatory: The 95% ethanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate used to extract *Ipomoea aquatica*.

- Naproxen used as positive control
- Distilled water used as negative control.
- Carrageenan used to induced-inflammatory
- 0.9% normal saline used to dilute carrageenan

Preparation of Extract

The plant sample of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves was cut into small pieces and dried. The dried sample was ground and macerated with 95% ethanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, and finally with ethyl acetate (5000 ml) for three days; this procedure was repeated two times. The extract was filtered, and after the filtration, it was evaporated to dryness under a rotary evaporator at a controlled temperature at 50°C.

Physical Test

The *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves extract were tested from its color and odor.

Animals

In vivo testing was performed on adult Sprague Dawley rats (100 g-220 g) of either sex. They were kept in regular laboratory settings and given ad libitum access to standard animal feed and water. The experimental protocol was approved by the institutional animal ethical committee (Moektiwardoyo et al., 2014).

Inflammatory Testing

The anti-inflammatory efficacy of several extracts of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves was tested using the carrageenan-induced paw oedema technique (Abdel-Aleem et al., 2019). Rats (100-220 g) were divided randomly into six groups (nine rats per group) for three (3) trials for oral gavage treatment once a day for seven (7) days.

The different extract was administered orally at a dose level of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg through 1 hour after carrageenan injection (0.1 ml, 1% w/v in normal saline, s.c.) into the sub-plantar tissue of the right hind paw of each rat.

For the control group, 1 ml distilled water was given in the left hind paw; positive treatment group (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg naproxen). The paw thickness (mm) will be measure using a vernier caliper at 0, 24, 48, 72, 96, 120, and 144 hours after administration of the tested extracts and standard drug.

Results and Discussion

How are the *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves to be extracted?

Ipomoea aquatica leaves were extracted by maceration. Grinded *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves were submerged for three (3) days in a 1000 mL beaker with 95% ethanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate and filtered using filter paper. A rotary evaporator was used to extract the solvent.

Will the *Ipomoea aquatica* leaf extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory activity?

1. Negative controls (Distilled water)
2. Positive controls (Naproxen)
3. Ethanol extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves
4. Chloroform extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves
5. Ethyl acetate extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves
6. Petroleum ether extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves

Table 1. Summary of measurements for the negative control group (Distilled water) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.
1 ml/dose Negative (Distilled water)	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.2 mm	1 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm

The table 1 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the negative control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 100 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using Vernier caliper.

Table 2. Summary of measurements for the positive control group (Naproxen) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.
100 mg/dose Positive (Naproxen)	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 2 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours using positive control.

Table 3. Summary of measurements for the 95% ethanol control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
100 mg/dose 95% Ethanol Extract	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 3 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using 95% ethanol control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 100 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 4. Summary of measurements for the petroleum ether control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
100 mg/dose Petroleum Ether Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.3 mm	0.7 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.3 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.3 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm

The table 4 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the petroleum ether control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 100 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 5. Summary of measurements for the chloroform control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
100 mg/dose Chloroform Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 5 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using chloroform control groups as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 100 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 6. Summary of measurements for the ethyl acetate control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
100 mg/dose Ethyl Acetate Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	1 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 6 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using ethyl acetate control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 100 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using Vernier caliper.

Table 7. Summary of measurements for the negative control group (Distilled water) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
1 mL/dose Negative (Distilled water)	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm

The table 7 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the negative control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 1 mL/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 8. Summary of measurements for the positive control group (Naproxen) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
200 mg/dose Positive (Naproxen)	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm

The table 8 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the positive control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 200 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 9. Summary of measurements for the 95% ethanol control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
200 mg/dose 95% Ethanol Extract	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm

The table 9 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using 95% ethanol control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 200 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 10. Summary of measurements for the petroleum ether control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
200 mg/dose Petroleum Ether Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm

The table 10 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the petroleum ether control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 200 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 11. Summary of measurements for the chloroform control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
200 mg/dose Chloroform Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm

The table 11 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using chloroform control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 200 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 12. Summary of measurements for the ethyl acetate control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
200 mg/dose Ethyl Acetate Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 12 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using ethyl acetate control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 200 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 13. Summary of measurements for the negative control group (Distilled water) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
1 mL/dose Negative (Distilled water)	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm

The table 13 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the negative control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 1 mL/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 14. Summary of measurements for the positive control group (Naproxen) before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
400 mg/dose Positive (Naproxen)	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 14 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the positive control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 400 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 15. Summary of measurements for the 95% ethanol control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
400 mg/dose 95% Ethanol Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.2 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 15 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using 95% ethanol control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 400 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 16. Summary of measurements for the petroleum ether control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
400 mg/dose Petroleum Ether Extract	Trial 1	0.3 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm
		0.3 mm	1 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm

The table 16 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using the petroleum ether control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 400 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 17. Summary of measurements for the chloroform control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
400 mg/dose Chloroform Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
	Trial 2	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	1 mm	0.9 mm	0.9 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.8 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 17 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using chloroform control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 400 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 18. Summary of measurements for the ethyl acetate control group before and after administration

Group	Trials	Before injection	Before oral	0 hr.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	120 hrs.	144 hrs.	
400 mg/dose Ethyl Acetate Extract	Trial 1	0.2 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	
		0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm	0.6 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	
	Trial 2	0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
		0.2 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
	Trial 3	0.3 mm	0.9 mm	0.7 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	0.8 mm	0.7 mm	0.6 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm
		0.3 mm	1 mm	0.7 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.4 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.3 mm

The table 18 data above showed the measure of inflammation in the right hind paw of rats before and after inducing carrageenan. The data represent the time frame from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours. Using ethyl acetate control group as a treatment for trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3 in 400 mg/dose and extract shows different values of measurements in every rat using vernier caliper.

Table 19. Summary of data from the mean report of trial 144 hours, the different extracts and concentration of the treatment

Treatments	Trial 144 Hours
Negative (Distilled water)	0.4778
Positive (Naproxen)	0.2444
95% Ethanol 100 mg/dose	0.4111
95% Ethanol 200 mg/dose	0.4000
95% Ethanol 400 mg/dose	0.3000
Petroleum Ether 100 mg/dose	0.3667
Petroleum Ether 200 mg/dose	0.3778
Petroleum Ether 400 mg/dose	0.3111
Chloroform 100 mg/dose	0.3889
Chloroform 200 mg/dose	0.5333
Chloroform 400 mg/dose	0.3111
Ethyl Acetate 100 mg/dose	0.3556
Ethyl Acetate 200 mg/dose	0.2556
Ethyl Acetate 400 mg/dose	0.2556

The table 19 data gathered showed that *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory effect but among the different extracts the ethyl acetate is the closest to the standard drug (Naproxen). The 144 hours also shows the optimal effect of the treatment with different concentration and extract; the mean from 144 hours was calculated and the result showed that among the different extracts and concentration the extracts of ethyl acetate in 200 mg/dose and 400 mg/dose are the closest to the standard drugs (Naproxen).

In what concentration does *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves extract exhibit anti-inflammatory activity?

Table 20. Summary of data from the mean report of the different extracts and concentration of the treatment

Treatments	Trial 0 hours	Trial 24 hours	Trial 48 hours	Trial 72 hours	Trial 96 hours	Trial 120 hours	Trial 144 hours
Negative (Distilled Water)	0.8556	0.6667	0.5333	0.7444	0.4889	0.4778	0.4778
Positive (Naproxen)	0.7556	0.5333	0.4889	0.6222	0.4000	0.3000	0.2444
95% Ethanol 100 Mg/Dose	0.7778	0.6222	0.5667	0.7000	0.5556	0.4333	0.4111
95% Ethanol 200 Mg/Dose	0.7000	0.6111	0.5556	0.6778	0.4667	0.4000	0.4000
95% Ethanol 400 Mg/Dose	0.5889	0.5000	0.4333	0.5444	0.3889	0.3333	0.3000
Pet Ether 100 Mg/Dose	0.7778	0.5444	0.4778	0.6444	0.4333	0.4111	0.3667
Pet Ether 200 Mg/Dose	0.6667	0.5667	0.5333	0.6222	0.5000	0.4333	0.3778
Pet Ether 400 Mg/Dose	0.6778	0.5889	0.4889	0.6222	0.4444	0.3667	0.3111
Chloroform 100 Mg/Dose	0.7222	0.5556	0.4778	0.6111	0.4333	0.4000	0.3889
Chloroform 200 Mg/Dose	0.6778	0.6667	0.6556	0.6667	0.6000	0.5333	0.5333
Chloroform 400 Mg/Dose	0.7000	0.5667	0.4556	0.6889	0.4000	0.3222	0.3111
Ethyl Acetate 100 Mg/Dose	0.7333	0.5778	0.5111	0.6222	0.4444	0.4111	0.3556
Ethyl Acetate 200 Mg/Dose	0.5667	0.4556	0.4444	0.5111	0.3778	0.3111	0.2556
Ethyl Acetate 400 Mg/Dose	0.5444	0.4556	0.3778	0.5111	0.3000	0.2889	0.2556
Total	0.6960	0.5651	0.5000	0.6278	0.4452	0.3873	0.3563

The table 20 shows the summary of data from the mean report of the different extracts and concentrations of the treatment from 0 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours and 144 hours. The report shows that in the different extract, ethyl acetate 200mg/dose and 400mg/dose is used most closely with the standard drug (Naproxen) results.

Is there any significant difference in the anti-inflammatory effect in various solvent?

Figure 1. Summary of data from the mean report of the different extracts and concentration of the treatment

This graph showed the duration of treatment from 0 hour, 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, 120 hours, and 144 hours using different extracts and concentrations. 144 hours shows that the treatment takes the optimal effect. It shows that the mean of ethyl acetate 200mg/dose and 400mg/dose are comparable and closest to standard drugs.

Will the plant *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory effect similar to standard?

Figure 2. Summary of data from the mean report of the different extracts and concentration of the treatment

The figure 2 graph showed that among the various solvents with different concentrations the ethyl acetate with 200 mg/dose and 400 mg/dose is the closest to the standard group.

Table 21. Comparison of different concentration and extract to the standard group (Naproxen)

Group Vs Group	Mean Vs Mean	P Value	Interpretation
Distilled Water vs. Naproxen	0.4778 +/- 0.04 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.000 < 0.05 sig	Not comparable
Ethyl acetate 400 vs. Naproxen	0.2556 +/-0.05 0.244 +/-0.05	p=1 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Ethyl acetate 200 vs. Naproxen	0.2556 +/- 0.07 0.244 +/-0.05	p=1 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Ethyl acetate 100 vs. Naproxen	0.3556 +/- 0.08 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.406 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Chloroform 400 vs. Naproxen	0.3111 +/- 0.03 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.980 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Chloroform 200 vs. Naproxen	0.5333 +/-0.21 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.000 < 0.05 sig	Not comparable
Chloroform 100 vs. Naproxen	0.3889 +/- 0.06 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.061 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Pet ether 400 vs. Naproxen	0.3111 +/- 0.06 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.980 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Pet ether 200 vs. Naproxen	0.3778 +/- 0.08 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.128 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
Pet ether 100 vs. Naproxen	0.3667 +/-0.05 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.242 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
95% Ethanol 400 vs. Naproxen	0.3000 +/-0.00 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.997 > 0.05 INS	Comparable
95% Ethanol 200 vs. Naproxen	0.4000 +/-0.08 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.027 < 0.05 sig	Not comparable
95% Ethanol 100 vs. Naproxen	0.4111 +/-0.07 0.244 +/-0.05	p=0.011 < 0.05 sig	Not comparable

Table 21 shows the comparison of different concentrations and extract to the standard group (Naproxen). Majority of the extracts are comparable to the standard drugs. The mean from 144 hours was calculated and the result showed that among the different extracts and concentration, the extracts of ethyl acetate in 200 mg/dose and 400 mg/dose are the closest to the standard drugs (Naproxen).

The study was conducted for assessing the potential of water spinach leaves (*Ipomoea aquatica* Forsk., Family: Convolvulaceae) extracts used as an anti-inflammatory agent. *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves were extracted by maceration. Grinded *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves were submerged for three (3) days in a 1000 mL beaker with 95% ethanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate and filtered using filter paper. The solvent was removed with the use of a rotary evaporator.

To achieve the goals, an experimental method was used for the assessment and gathering of data. Different concentrations of *Ipomoea aquatica* were prepared which are 100 mg/dose, 200 mg/dose, and 400 mg/dose and used as a treatment for anti-inflammatory activity along with distilled water for negative control and naproxen for positive control in the carrageenan-induced rat paw edema. The plant *Ipomoea aquatica* contains various phytochemicals such as flavonoids, aliphatic pyrrolidine amides, glycosides, prostaglandin and even amino acids.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the extract of *Ipomoea aquatica* has anti-inflammatory characteristics that are most likely mediated by suppression of prostaglandin formation, which could be useful in the treatment of pain and inflammatory illnesses. Prostaglandins are potent local vasodilators that prevent blood platelets from adhering together. Prostaglandins play a function in inflammation through their role in vasodilation. Also, the significance of the ethyl acetate extract may contribute to their high content of flavonoids. Flavonoids are a wide range of phytochemicals with various pharmacological effects. Some of the study linked that the flavonoid contains from the leaves might be considerable in the anti-inflammatory potential.

The flavonoids extract has a resemblance with the positive control (Naproxen) because the study found them to be comparable. The positive control and the extract were found to be 0.2444 mm and 0.2556 mm respectively after 144 hours trial, which show no significant difference.

Naproxen and the flavonoid extract are both aromatic compounds but differ at their functional groups; naproxen has carboxylic acid while the flavonoid extract has phenol and ketone, which makes each of their mechanisms of action to differ from the other. Naproxen is involved in the reduction of prostaglandin synthesis by the inhibition of COX-2 enzyme through competitive antagonism for arachidonic acid by binding to the cyclooxygenase enzyme, while the flavonoids inhibit kinases by competitively binding with ATP at catalytic sites on the enzymes. Signal transduction and cell activation activities involving immune system cells are mediated by these enzymes. Flavonoids have been shown to reduce the expression of isoforms of inducible nitric oxide synthase, cyclooxygenase, and lipoxygenase, all of which are involved in the synthesis of nitric oxide, prostanoids, leukotrienes, and other inflammatory mediators. Phosphodiesterase, which is involved in cell activation, is similarly reduced by flavonoids. More circulating leukocytes are attracted to injury sites (Kumar and Pandey, 2013).

In the present investigation, the ethyl acetate extract with the concentration of 200mg/dose and 400 mg/dose showed the closest effect compared to the standard (Naproxen) while the other groups showed a mild inhibition of the inflammation in carrageenan-induced paw edema. When tissue is exposed to any inflammation causes, the prostaglandin increases tissue sensitivity to pain. As a result, cell membranes release arachidonic acid by partial lipid hydrolysis by the membrane associated enzyme phospholipase (Al-Turki et al., 2010). Arachidonic acid has two biochemical transformations such as lipoxygenase and cyclooxygenase.

Naproxen acts as anti-inflammatory agent by inhibiting the biosynthesis of the prostaglandin that is classified as treatment of inflammation, this chemical act in reduction of prostaglandin synthesis through the inhibition of COX enzyme competitive antagonism for arachidonic acid by binding to the cyclooxygenase enzyme.

Flavonoids have the ability to intervene on the function of enzyme systems involved in the development of inflammatory processes. Certain flavonoids are effective inhibitors of prostaglandin synthesis, a class of anti-inflammatory signaling chemicals (Nile et al., 2018). Hesperidin, apigenin, luteolin, and quercetin are flavonoids that have anti-inflammatory properties. Flavonoids have been shown to decrease the expression of isoforms of inducible nitric oxide synthase, cyclooxygenase, and lipoxygenase, all of which are involved in the inflammatory process (Katkar et al., 2010).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Ipomoea aquatica exhibits anti-inflammatory activity and can serve as a home remedy for treatment and prevention of inflammation. In the present study, the results showed that the treatment that we used is comparable to the standard drug (Naproxen).

Among the treatment groups the result indicated that the ethyl acetate extract with various concentrations has significant anti-inflammatory property closest to the standard drug (Naproxen) (Azeem et al., 2010). The ethyl acetate extract can be an effective therapeutic agent in the treatment of inflammations. It might be that the flavonoid contained in the *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves gives anti-inflammatory activity.

In line with results, the researchers recommended the following:

1. Further studies using the other parts of the plant *Ipomoea aquatica* for anti-inflammatory activity.
2. Use different solvent in the treatment of inflammation.
3. Explore different methods for the extraction of the plant.
4. Investigate other constituents other than flavonoids which may be responsible for the anti-inflammatory activity.
5. Demonstrate the possible mechanism of actions of *Ipomoea aquatica* leaves extract for anti-inflammatory activity.
6. Further studies of *Ipomoea aquatica* for the different activity of the plant.
7. Continue with the experiment.

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